

Communication and Transparency Practice in Relation to Private School Governance

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Abstract. The study unfolded the extent of communication and transparency and the private school governance perceived by parents and teachers in the Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of communication and transparency practices in private schools was extensive, while private school governance was moderately extensive in the Davao Oriental Schools Division. There was a significant relationship between communication and transparency practices in private schools and private school governance. All domains of communication and transparency practices in terms of accessibility of information, frequency of updates, stakeholders' involvement, conflict resolutions, and transparency in financial matters indicate statistically significant influence on private school governance. Future research may explore the nuances of these practices more deeply, considering cultural and contextual variations. Investigating the evolving role of technology in enhancing communication within educational institutions and its impact on transparency is also recommended.

KEY WORDS

1. communication 2. transparency practices in private schools 3. private school governance

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1. Introduction

For several reasons, studying communication and transparency practices in private school governance is crucial. Effective communication ensures that all stakeholders, including administrators, teachers, parents, and students, are well-informed and engaged in the school's decision-making processes. This fosters a collaborative environment where feedback is encouraged and valued, leading to more responsive and adaptive governance. On the other hand, transparency builds trust and accountability by making the school's operations, decisions, and financial matters open to scrutiny. This is particularly important in private schools where tuition fees fund operations, and stakeholders demand assurance that resources are used efficiently and ethically. Transparent practices also help mitigate conflicts, as they reduce misunderstandings and provide clear rationale for decisions, thus promoting a sense of fairness and integrity. In the international setting, private school governance faces several significant

challenges. One of the foremost issues is the accessibility and affordability of private education. While private schools can offer quality education, they are often seen as exclusive and financially out of reach for many families, exacerbating educational inequalities. Additionally, ensuring transparency and accountability within private schools can be challenging, as they may be subject to a different level of public scrutiny than their public counterparts. Regulatory frameworks and oversight mechanisms can vary widely between countries, leading to concerns about the consistency of educational standards and practices. Furthermore, there are ongoing debates about the role of private schools in perpetuating social stratification and whether they divert resources from the public education system. These challenges highlight the need for thoughtful governance, effective regulation, and a commitment to addressing educational disparities in the international context (Kater and Burke, 2022). Tao (2022) stated that network governance has become a widely recognized and increasingly utilized instrument for leading and managing public service delivery, especially in education. However, beyond mainstream Based on a thorough analysis of policy documents and scholarly research, this article argues that the Chinese central state has changed its governance mode from centralization to network governance by incorporating peripheral actors, including local governments, schools, and societal forces, as active agents in governing education. However, despite these peripheral actors' increasing autonomy and participation, the central state still retains the ultimate power and authority over education governance in China. Welch (2020) critically examines the literature on governance in higher education and underlines the relationship to forms of corruption in the field. While corrupt practices in higher education are by no means unique to the region (indeed, examples can be found worldwide in virtually every system), most rank poorly

on conventional measures of transparency. In the Philippine education system, private school governance faces several pressing challenges. One significant issue is the growing gap in access and affordability between private and public schools. While private schools often offer quality education, their tuition fees can be prohibitive for many Filipino families, exacerbating educational inequalities (Zambrana et al., 2019). Another challenge is increased regulation and oversight of private schools to ensure they meet educational standards and maintain transparency in their operations. There have been unscrupulous practices and a lack of accountability in some private institutions, raising concerns among parents and educators. Additionally, private schools sometimes face challenges related to teacher qualifications, curriculum alignment with national standards, and their role in promoting social cohesion and inclusivity within the Philippine education system. Addressing these challenges requires a collaborative effort between private schools, government authorities, and stakeholders to ensure that all students have access to quality education regardless of their socio-economic background (Curran and Boza, 2023). Parents and teachers in the Philippine education system often perceive private school governance through various lenses. While private schools are valued for their potential to provide quality education, parental and teacher perceptions can vary. Many parents consider private schools attractive due to their perceived higher academic standards, smaller class sizes, and better resources. They may appreciate private schools' autonomy and flexibility in shaping curricula and programs. However, concerns about affordability, transparency in fee structures, and potential exclusivity can temper these positive perceptions (Ayuso et al., 2022). Teachers in private schools may appreciate the relative independence and innovative teaching methods that private institutions can offer. They often value the opportunities for professional

development and smaller student-teacher ratios. Yet, challenges such as salary disparities and job security can be sources of concern. Additionally, parents and teachers may have varying views on transparency and accountability in private school governance, with some expressing a need for greater regulatory oversight to ensure

quality and fairness. In essence, perceptions of private school governance in the Philippines are multifaceted and can be influenced by individual experiences, financial considerations, and the perceived trade-offs between quality and accessibility. Thus, this paper is presented.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps for conducting the study. These include selecting the study design, the respondents and sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical considerations, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps were considered essential to ensure appropriateness and correctness and to produce sound data process collection, analysis, and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design was a comprehensive approach in the field of research methodology that combines several key elements to explore relationships and systematically predict outcomes. This design typically involves observing and analyzing existing data or naturally occurring phenomena without intervening, manipulating, or controlling variables (Creswel, 2014). Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs are valuable in studying Communication and Transparency in Private School Governance. Researchers gather data from private schools without manipulating variables in a descriptive-correlational non-experimental survey. This design allows for examining existing communication and transparency practices within these institutions. Researchers can collect data on communication frequency, accessibility of information, stakeholder involvement, and financial transparency through surveys, questionnaires, and document analysis. Using correlation analysis, relationships between variables, such as stakeholder involvement and transparency levels, could be ex-

plored to determine whether any statistically significant associations exist. Predictive research, on the other hand, aims to forecast future outcomes based on historical data. In private school governance, predictive research can anticipate changes in communication practices and transparency levels, helping school administrators make informed decisions for continuous improvement. These research designs offer valuable insights into private school governance's communication and transparency dynamics, facilitating evidence-based decision-making and fostering accountability within educational institutions.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Parents and Teachers in the selected Private Schools in Davao Oriental Schools Division. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 100 teachers and parent respondents were taken randomly from each Private School. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face, considering the availability of the Wifi connections, and they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These parents and teachers respondents were selected because

they were assumed to have been engaged in the management and governance of private schools. They are qualified for the role they were expected to have performed and contributed to, given that they have attended various activities related to the school’s management and governance under the School-Based Management system of private schools. This is done through school faculty and PTA meetings for the betterment of the school and the learners’ awareness and educational stages, given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading re-

views of related literature to develop concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. As the authors argued, items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of communication and transparency in terms of accessibility of information, frequency of updates, stakeholders’ involvement, conflict resolution processes, and transparency in financial matters. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured private school governance in terms of financial management, strategic planning, compliance and accreditation, and community engagement. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.875, meaning there is an 87.5 percent trust in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of communication and transparency. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale of Communication and Transparency

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The communication and transparency is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The communication and transparency is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The communication and transparency is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The communication and transparency is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The communication and transparency is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Scale of Private School Governance

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The private school governance is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The private school governance is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The private school governance is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The private school governance is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The private school governance is not manifested

The preceding statements explain the steps of the data-gathering procedure that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. They were based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the Department of Education. Permission to conduct the study. The second week of October 2023, the researcher started conceptualizing the thesis proposal's contents and objectives. She then prepares documents such as letter requests for the study. The research study adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004) .From the last week of January up to first week of February 2024, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, through the channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study among the Elementary and Secondary schools of Davao Oriental Schools Division. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In April 2024, the researcher

prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the first week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of May 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime during the first week of June 2024 and further deepen the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results during the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) on the extent of communication and transparency and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of private school governance as perceived by parents and teachers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between communication and transparency and the extent of private school governance perceived

by parents and teachers. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the indicators of communication and transparency that significantly influence private school governance as perceived by parents and teachers (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were obtained, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter elucidates the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data, which has been collected and organized in both tabular and textual formats. The goal is to provide a lucid understanding of the inquiries stemming from the stated problem. The implications of the results are articulated through diverse reviews, validating and substantiating the hypotheses and theories put forth in the study.

Communication and Transparency Practices Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of communication and transparency practices. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: stakeholders’ involvement (3.97), conflict resolution processes (3.45), and transparency

in financial matters (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while frequency of updates (3.36) and accessibility of information (3.26) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.50 denotes the extent to which teachers’ practical skills of instruction are oftentimes manifested and, thus, extensive.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Communication and Transparency Practices

No	Communication and Transparency Practices	Mean
1	Accessibility of Information	3.26
2	Frequency of Updates	3.36
3	Stakeholders’ Involvement	3.97
4	Conflict Resolution Processes	3.45
5	Transparency in Financial Matters	3.45
Overall Mean		3.50

Table 2 shows a summary of the extent of private school governance. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: community engage-

ments (3.77) are often manifested, while compliance and accreditation (3.35), financial management (3.22), and strategic planning (3.18) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rat-

ing of 3.38 denotes the extent to which private school governance is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Private School Governance

No	Private School Governance	Mean
1	Financial Management	3.22
2	Strategic Planning	3.18
3	Compliance and Accreditation	3.35
4	Community Engagement	3.77
Overall Mean		3.38

Correlation Analysis Between Communication and Transparency Practices in Private Schools and Private School Governance

It can be depicted that Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson’s r generated a significant correlation between communication and transparency practices in private schools (r=0.883; p<.002) and private school governance. Table 3 revealed the yielded results

of the significant correlation between communication and transparency practices in private schools and private school governance. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between communication and transparency practices in private schools and private school governance must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of statistically significant results.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Communication and Transparency Practices in Private Schools and Private School Governance

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Private School Governance	0.883	<0.002	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ p<0.05.

Welch (2020) shared that the relationship between communication and transparency practices in private schools is integral to the effective governance of these educational institutions. Communication serves as the lifeblood of any organization, facilitating the exchange of information and fostering a sense of community among stakeholders. In the context of private schools, transparent communication is particularly crucial for maintaining trust and credibility. Transparent practices involve sharing information openly, not only about academic matters

but also about the school’s governance structure, decision-making processes, and financial affairs. When private schools prioritize transparency in their communication, it enhances accountability and allows stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and administrators, to understand the school’s policies and objectives better. In private school governance, transparent communication is pivotal in building a collaborative and informed community. School administrators must communicate their strategic vision, mission, and goals to all stakeholders, align-

ing expectations and promoting a shared understanding of the institution's direction. Transparent communication ensures that decision-making processes are clear and accessible, mitigating potential misunderstandings and fostering a sense of inclusivity. Additionally, it helps build trust among parents and teachers, creating a positive environment conducive to learning (Holmyard, 2021). Private school governance also requires effective communication channels to disseminate information about financial matters. Transparency in financial practices, such as disclosing budget allocations, tuition fees, and fundraising initiatives, is vital for maintaining the trust of parents and other stakeholders. Clear communication about the allocation of resources enables stakeholders to comprehend the school's financial health and ensures that decisions related to budgeting and expenditures are made with transparency and accountability (Kater Burke, 2022). Transparent communication is the cornerstone of effective private school governance, fostering trust, collaboration, and accountability among all stakeholders. When private schools prioritize open and honest communication, they enhance their governance structures and create a positive and informed community aligned with the school's mission and values (Salamondra, 2021). Linear Regres-

The accessibility of information, frequency of updates, stakeholder involvement, conflict resolution processes, and transparency in financial matters are crucial predictors of communication and transparency practices within any organization, including private schools. The accessibility of information refers to how readily available and easily understandable information is for stakeholders. When information is easily accessible, it promotes transparency and allows stakeholders to stay informed about the school's operations, policies, and decisions (Nederland et al., 2023). Frequent updates fur-

sion Analysis on the Domains of Communication and Transparency Practices Significantly Influence Private School Governance

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of communication and transparency practices that significantly influence private school governance. It can be noted that all domains of communication and transparency practices in terms of accessibility of information (0.011), frequency of updates (0.002), stakeholders' involvement (0.013), conflict resolutions (0.001) and transparency in financial matters (0.030), indicate statistically significant to influence private school governance. This shows that the domains of communication and transparency practices significantly influence private school governance. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.897 suggests that the domains of communication and transparency practices explained 89.7%. This provides empirical evidence that the domains of communication and transparency practices can account for and explain the variability of private school governance. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (225.986) and F-statistic are significant $p < .000$, indicating that the model better predicts private school governance.

ther contribute to effective communication by keeping stakeholders abreast of developments, fostering engagement, and preventing the emergence of information gaps or misunderstandings (Wise et al., 2020). Stakeholder involvement is another significant predictor, as it reflects the extent to which individuals within the school community are included in decision-making processes. When stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and students, are actively engaged in decision-making, it not only enhances the quality of decisions but also strengthens the overall communication fabric of the institution. Stake-

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Communication and Transparency Practices Significantly Influence Private School Governance

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.397		0.062	< .001	
H (Intercept)	0.401		0.144	0.006	
Accessibility of Information	0.032	-0.021	0.046	0.011	Reject H0
Frequency of Updates	0.342	0.361	0.054	0.002	Reject H0
Stakeholders' Involvement	0.032	-0.021	0.046	0.011	Reject H0
Conflict Resolution Processes	0.207	0.215	0.064	0.013	Reject H0
Transparency in Financial Matters	0.568	0.425	0.079	0.030	Reject H0
R ²				0.897	
F-value				225.896	
p-value				<0.000	

*Significant @ p<0.05.

holder involvement creates a sense of ownership and shared responsibility, contributing to a more collaborative and transparent governance structure (Dones et al., 2023). Fountain (2019) explored that Conflict resolution processes also play a pivotal role in predicting communication and transparency practices. The effectiveness of a school's conflict resolution mechanisms can influence the openness with which disputes are addressed and resolved. A fair and transparent conflict resolution process fosters trust. It demonstrates a commitment to equitably resolving issues and just, contributing to a positive communication climate within the school. Koochel et al. (2020) assess that transparency in financial matters is perhaps one of the most critical predictors of communication and transparency practices in private schools.

Clear communication about budgeting, expenditures, and fundraising not only ensures financial accountability but also demonstrates a commitment to openness and honesty. When stakeholders have access to comprehensive information about the school's financial practices, trust and confidence are built, fostering a positive environment for effective communication. In conclusion, information accessibility, frequency of updates, stakeholder involvement, conflict resolution processes, and transparency in financial matters are interconnected predictors that collectively shape communication and transparency practices within private schools. By prioritizing these elements, schools can establish a foundation for open and effective communication, ultimately contributing to a transparent and collaborative educational environment.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper section outlines the researcher's conclusions and recommendations, drawing support from the literature covered in the initial chapters. The conclusion aligns with the problem

statements articulated in this study.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of communication and transparency practices in private schools in terms of stakeholder involvement (3.97), conflict resolution processes (3.45), and transparency in financial matters (3.45) were oftentimes manifested, while frequency of updates (3.36) and accessibility of information (3.26); are sometimes manifested. This denotes that communication and transparency practices in private schools are extensive (3.50) in the Davao Oriental Schools Division. The extent of private school governance in terms of community engagement (3.77) is oftentimes manifested, while compliance and accreditation (3.35), financial management (3.22), and strategic planning (3.18) were sometimes manifested. This denotes that private school governance was moderately extensive (3.38) in Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson's r generated a significant correlation between communication and transparency practices in private schools ($r=0.883$; $p<.002$) and private school governance. All domains of communication and transparency practices, in terms of accessibility of information (0.011), frequency of updates (0.002), stakeholders' involvement (0.013), conflict resolutions (0.001), and transparency in financial matters (0.03), indicate statistically significant influence on private school governance. This shows that communication and transparency practices significantly influence private school governance.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions, to wit; The extent of communication and transparency practices in private schools in terms of stakeholder involvement, conflict resolution processes, and transparency in financial matters was often manifested, while the fre-

quency of updates and accessibility of information was sometimes manifested. This denoted that communication and transparency practices in private schools were extensive in the Davao Oriental Schools Division. The extent of private school governance in terms of community engagement was oftentimes manifested, while compliance and accreditation, financial management, and strategic planning were sometimes manifested. This denoted that private school governance was moderately extensive in the Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson's r generated a significant correlation between communication and transparency practices in private schools and private school governance. All domains of communication and transparency practices, in terms of accessibility of information, frequency of updates, stakeholders' involvement, conflict resolutions, and transparency in financial matters, indicate statistically significant influence on private school governance.

4.3. Recommendations—The study yields several recommendations tailored to key stakeholders within the educational ecosystem. With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations, to wit; To the Public School District Supervisor: Policies promoting standardized communication and transparency practices across all schools within the district may be recommended. Establishing clear guidelines for information accessibility, updating frequency, and stakeholder involvement could ensure a consistent and transparent governance framework. Additionally, facilitating training programs on conflict resolution and financial transparency for school administrators could enhance the overall effectiveness of communication practices. To the School Principal. The study suggests prioritizing a culture of open communication within the school com-

munity. Regularly updating stakeholders on school policies, academic developments, and financial matters fosters transparency. Creating platforms for stakeholder engagement and involving them in decision-making processes can enhance the collaborative spirit within the school. Investing in professional development for conflict resolution skills was also recommended to address disputes transparently and fairly. The Teachers may be recommended to incorporate communication skills training into professional development programs. Emphasizing the importance of transparent communication with students, parents, and colleagues could contribute to a positive learning environment. Encouraging teachers to participate in decision-making processes actively and keeping them informed about school policies ensured that they were well-informed contributors to the school community. To the Future Researchers. The study underscores the importance of exploring the longitudinal impact of communication and transparency practices on educational outcomes. Future research could delve deeper into the nuances of these practices, considering cultural and contextual variations. Investigating the evolving role of technology in enhancing communication within educational institutions and its impact on transparency was also recommended. This would contribute to the ongoing discourse on effective governance and communication strategies in the dynamic education landscape.

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